

Analyzing the Influence of Food and Cultural Tourism on Destination Development A Case Study of Jaunsar Bawar, Uttarakhand

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ABSTRACT

Purpose – This paper aims to explore the significance of local food and culture in positioning an area as a tourist destination. It offers insights into various initiatives in the realm of food and cultural tourism and their implementation processes within Jaunsar Bawar.

Design/methodology/approach – This study adopts an exploratory approach, employing qualitative primary research methodology with a non-random stratified sampling method. Semi-structured, open-ended face-to-face interviews were conducted with 20 respondents representing diverse fields in Jaunsar Bawar. Additionally, the author's personal experience and secondary data sources were utilized to complement the findings.

Findings -- The research indicates that Culture and Food are highly valued by visitors for enhancing their overall experience and creating lasting memories. Moreover, food and cultural tourism not only enhance the experience of inbound tourists but also stimulate the local economy.

Practical Implications

Similar to the rest of India, Jaunsar Bawar's social and religious fabric is woven with exotic cultural practices and culinary traditions. The rhythmic beats of festive drums inspire a culinary celebration, yielding an array of dishes cherished as 'soul food' by the Jaunsari tribe. Often, food plays a pivotal role in attracting tourists to a destination, serving as a reflection of its rich culture and lifestyle. Food is not merely a basic necessity for tourists; it embodies a cultural element that can profoundly shape their perception of a destination. The synergy between food, culture, and

tourism not only captivates tourists but also catalyzes social, economic, and environmental development. This paper underscores the interconnectedness of food, culture, and tourism in creating a distinctive destination brand in the minds of travelers. Each facet of Jaunsar Bawar in Uttarakhand boasts unique allure, capable of drawing tourists from across the globe. Leveraging the region's delectable cuisine and centuries-old cultural heritage can serve as a pivotal promotional tool for tourism development.

Despite its immense potential, the promotion of culture, food, and wine as key components of Jaunsar Bawar's destination appeal is still in its nascent stage. Establishing symbiotic relationships between the tourism and food production sectors can augment the region's economy while preserving and enriching local socio-economic dynamics.

This report delves into the strengths and opportunities of food promotion in Jaunsar Bawar through a comprehensive case study approach and the researcher's expertise. Additionally, it explores the distinctive cultural heritage features of Jaunsar Bawar and proposes strategies to enhance cultural awareness. Furthermore, the paper examines the pivotal role of local communities in promoting food tourism as an integral aspect of cultural heritage development.

Keywords: Tribal tourism, Cultural tourism, Jaunsar Bawar, Garhwal, Mythology, Gastronomy Tourism,

Introduction

The term "culture" refers to the complex collection of knowledge, folklore, language, rules, rituals, habits, lifestyles, attitudes, beliefs, and customs that present a common identity to a particular group of people at a specific point in time. All social units develop a culture. The inhabitants of a specific region collectively contribute to forming the extraordinary essence of life, which is called culture. The cultural history of Uttarakhand is very ancient, beginning with the advent of Aryans in India. Its cultural history has been referenced in the great epics of Ramayana and Mahabharata. The temples of Badrinath and Kedarnath depict its historical significance. Historians have different opinions on the arrival of Aryans and their early settlements. Some foreign historians suggest that after the arrival of Aryans in India, they first settled in hilly regions, including the Uttarakhand Himalaya. However, Indian historians have a different opinion, believing that the Aryans arrived and settled in the Ganges plain before migrating to the Uttarakhand Himalaya. Some historians, such as W. T. Henwood, Atkinson, Rahul Sankrityayan, Dr. Mauliya, and Mathpal, believe that human civilization flourished in the valleys of the Ganga and its tributaries. Due to numerous rivers originating and flowing in the

Uttarakhand Himalaya, it is believed that Uttarakhand was the early home of the Aryans and many other human races. The Kols, Kirats, Yakshas, Gandharvas, Kinnars, Nags, and Tangans are believed to be the oldest human races inhabiting the Uttarakhand Himalaya, as referred to in Hindu religious scriptures, including the Ramayana and Mahabharata. Apart from them, the Shaks, Khasas, and tribes are also among the oldest inhabitants. Uttarakhand had many small kingdoms, ruled by various rulers in the past, each with its cultural identity. Uttarakhand was known as Kedarkhand (the Garhwal region) and Manaskhand (the Kumaon region) in the past. It is called Dev-Bhumi. The Uttarakhand Himalaya consists of two distinct cultural and geographical entities: the Garhwal and Kumaon regions. The culture, rituals, and customs of both regions are different and have been performed since time immemorial. The people follow either the Shaiv cult or the Vaishnav cult. A large number of people are followers of Lord Shiva and Goddess Shakti. Lord Shiva, an adorable deity, has many incarnations, namely Mahadev, KalBhairav, and Kalua, which are considered as folk deities. Similarly, Goddess Shakti has several forms, including Durga, Bhagawati, and Gaura or Parwati. KalBhairav is believed to be one of the 52 incarnations of Lord Shiva. ² In the past, the custom of sacrificing animals to appease Gods and Goddesses was common among the followers of Lord Shiva. People used to offer goats to folk deities during fairs, festivals, and other auspicious occasions. However, over time, this custom has been abolished. 'Goril,' a folk deity, is believed to be an incarnation of 'Lord Rama,' and the followers of Vaishnav Cult worship Lord Goril. The food habits of the followers of both cults are different. While the Shaivs are non-vegetarian, the Vaishnavs are pure vegetarian. Every family has its folk deity – Kul Dev/Devi and Isht Dev/Devi. Gram Dev and Jungle Dev are other folk deities worshipped by rural people. People worship all folk deities on various occasions. Every first day of the Hindu calendar is known as Sankranti, and there are 12 Sankrantis celebrated in a year. Navratras, a continuous nine-day and night celebration, are observed in the months of Chaitra and Margshirsha. During Navratras, Dev/Devi Naach is performed. Folk deities that are believed to have appeared in human form are called Dev Avataran. Jagars are sung, and drummers play Dhol-Damau. The melodious sounds of drums, bands, and musical instruments create an enthusiastic and divinely charged environment. People worship folk deities for the peace, progress, and prosperity of their families and the well-being of society. Fruits, vegetables, sweets, and fresh food are offered to folk deities. Brahmins perform all rituals, and on all auspicious occasions, people from various castes and creeds, including Rajputs, Scheduled Tribes, and Scheduled Castes, invite Brahmins to conduct Puja in their

homes. Collective Puja is also organized by Brahmins, who have migrated from different parts of India, primarily from the Ganga valley. Records indicate that individuals such as Bahuguna migrated from Bengal, Bhatt from Gujarat and Maharashtra, and Dimri from Kashmir. Rajputs, who migrated to Uttarakhand, played a crucial role in guarding the pilgrimage centers. The Bhotiyas of Chamoli and Pithoragarh districts have a mixed culture. Before 1962, they had a trade relationship with Tibet and engaged in intermarriages. The three passes – Mana and Niti in the Chamoli district and Lipulekh in the Pithoragarh district – were the main routes for trade. Johar, a festival celebrated by Jads and Bhotiyas, is the primary festival of Tibetans. Lord Shiva is a revered deity worshipped throughout the entire Uttarakhand Himalaya, and this devotion is reflected in the day-to-day affairs of the people. Various sacred sites such as Kailash, Mansarovar, Chhota Kailash, PanchKedar, Jageshwar, and Bageshwar are considered the abode of Lord Shiva. Additionally, different forms of Goddess Shakti, including Nanda Devi, Naina Devi, Bhagawati, Surkanda Devi, Kunjapuri, and Chandrabadni, are worshipped in the region. Uttarakhand has been a land of peace, penance, and salvation for saints and sages (Rishis and Sadhus) since time immemorial. The Rishis undertook penance for the well-being— peace, progress, and prosperity—of the region's inhabitants. In the past, pupils learned scriptures in Guru Kulas (places of learning), where the Rishis served as their teachers. 3 Historical evidence suggests that the Uttarakhand Himalaya was also influenced by Buddhism. However, with the arrival of Adi Shankracharya in Uttarakhand during the 9th century AD, the people embraced Brahmin culture. Worshipping Lord Vishnu at Badrinath Dham is an ancient tradition, as depicted in the Skanda Purana. In this holy land, two sects, Matha and Arya Samaj, which are part of Hinduism, have established their presence. A group of people who adopted Buddhism within the Matha sect still maintains a deep faith in worshipping Lord Vishnu. The Arya Samaj, founded by Swami Dayanand Saraswati, has also left its imprint on Uttarakhand, with Swami Dayanand Saraswati visiting many places in the region. Life in the hills is exceptionally challenging for many people, with a significant portion being deprived of basic necessities such as food, shelter, and clothing. The terrain is rugged, and the climate can be harsh. Natural hazards are a common, intense, and frequent occurrence. The belief persists among the people that Gods and Goddesses reside in the high mountains, mountain tops, waterfalls, snow-covered peaks, rivers, streams, lakes, confluences, and the origins of rivers. There is a traditional belief that folk deities safeguard their lives during adverse situations. Describing Uttarakhand, Sherring states, 'In those lovely valleys, there is still the romance and poetry of life; each tree has its God, each bush its

spirit.' Sages and saints often choose these serene places for meditation, with the well-being of humanity being the focal point of their contemplation. The traditional culture and customs of Uttarakhand are deeply influenced by the dominance of nature, and in turn, nature leaves a profound imprint on the diversity of culture and customs. The mighty Himalayas play a pivotal role in shaping the daily life of the people, who worship the Himalayas in the forms of Lord Shiva and Shakti. Seasons, festivals, societies, cultures, customs, and the diversity in religion, castes, and creeds are intricately integrated into the natural surroundings. The people of the region maintain social integrity among diverse castes and creeds, celebrating fairs and festivals with great enthusiasm and collective spirit. Spiritual and religious activities are intertwined with nature, as people embark on journeys that align closely with the natural environment. Most cultural activities are associated with various forms of nature, including rivers, mountains, and agricultural practices. The Ganga, considered the most sacred river, becomes the focal point for rituals and pujas performed on its banks. Morning and evening aartis are carried out daily. Additionally, riverbanks serve as important centers for performing funeral rituals. Cities and towns along the Ganga valley, from its source to where it meets the Bay of Bengal, serve as significant cultural centers for various customs and rituals. Notable cultural centers include Gangotri, Uttarkashi, Devprayag, Rishikesh, Haridwar, Prayagraj, Varanasi, Patna, and Ganga Sagar. Despite having distinct cultural identities, there is harmony among all groups of people. Indigenous people, referred to as Scheduled Tribes and Scheduled Castes, 4 have thrived in the region while preserving their cultural identity. The pilgrimages of Uttarakhand, situated in valleys and highland sacred places, contribute to the integration of the nationhood. The priests in the Badrinath temple, for instance, belong to Kerala, specifically the Namboodaries Brahmins. Major centers for attaining spirituality include Panch Badri, PanchKedar, and PanchPrayag. Rishikesh and Haridwar, two ancient cultural places, attract pilgrims from around the world who come to perform customs and rituals. The cultural significance of Uttarakhand is not only upheld through present-day practices but is also deeply rooted in legends, myths, tales, and scriptures. The Uttarakhand Himalaya, an integral part of the larger Himalayan range, stands out as a unique custodian and preserver of Indian culture. Serving as a focal point for Indian philosophy, spirituality, religion, and cultural diversity over centuries, this region has been a place of penance and spiritual enlightenment. The Uttarakhand Himalaya holds the distinction of being the birthplace of Rishis, saints, and sages since time immemorial. People from all walks of life, belonging to various religions, castes, and creeds, visit the sacred pilgrimages, valleys,

highlands, and tourist destinations throughout the year. As a result, the culture of the region has been significantly shaped by the modern waves of civilization, both from within India and abroad. The ancient pilgrimages, situated in highlands and river valleys of Uttarakhand, have flourished over the years. These pilgrimage centers, serving as focal points for attaining peace, spirituality, and salvation, not only showcase cultural integrity but also play a vital role in preserving folk culture. They serve as significant sources of inspiration and aspirations for the people. Pilgrims visit these sacred sites with the aim of liberating souls from the cycle of birth and death. In the remote areas of the Uttarakhand Himalaya, traditional culture, customs, and rituals have been conserved, reflecting the deep-rooted heritage of the region. However, the river valleys and cultural places have undergone significant changes over time. In addition to the influence of Hinduism, these pilgrimage centers have also been impacted by Buddhism, Jainism, and Sikhism. The migration of Tibetans to Uttarakhand has left an imprint on the local culture, contributing to the diversity and richness of the cultural tapestry in the region. This study delves into culture and the cultural realms of the Uttarakhand Himalaya, providing a division and description of these realms. Furthermore, it explores sub-cultural and micro-cultural realms within these broader cultural classifications. The cultural regions are also examined based on dialects, offering insights into the linguistic diversity and cultural intricacies of the Uttarakhand Himalaya.

Review of Literature

Cultural & Heritage Tourism

Resource Persons and Year of Publication	Views Regarding role of local food as Destination Attraction
(Timothy & Boyd, 2003).	Literature has acknowledged that history and culture are intertwined because "culture is the current application of the aspects of the past"
(Turnbridge & Asworth, 1996).	"Heritage is what contemporary society chooses to inherit and pass on to future generations, whereas history is what a historian deems worthy of documenting"
Ahmed (2006),	Heritage sites are those that aid in the comprehension of the past, enhance the present, and will be of importance to future generations. For the places of archeological and architectural values, it is the people and activities that form the cultural heritage.

(Edgell , 2006).	Culture consists of the valuable items inherited from previous generations. If the value is local or national, we refer to it as our legacy
(Advisory Council on Historic Preservation, 2002).	. Cultural and historic visitors stay longer and spend more money than other types of tourists, making cultural and heritage tourism an essential instrument for economic growth
(Busby & Rendle, 2000; Veeck, Chee, & Veeck, 2006).	It is possible to find gastronomy tourism in both rural and urban regions, and visitors should be able to come year-round. Consequently, its potential for enhancing food safety and security in Jaunsar Bawar should be evaluated. Relevant literature includes specialty tourism, agritourism, Gastronomy tourism, food-based attractions, and food-purchasing incentives. For instance, agritourism (farm tourism) specializes in the inclusion of farm visits for on-site retail sales, leisure, and education
(Long, 2004)	As a means of consuming different locations and cultures, gastronomy tourism also examines the behaviors of exploratory eating and participation in possibly foreign food ways.

Possibilities of Cultural Tourism

As Jaunsar bawar is a hilly area where Jaunsari tribes have been existing for hundreds of years. These tribes have their own culture in terms of folk dances, songs, festivals, temples and monuments, sports during culture events which are quite popular among themselves, but for the rest of the world these cultural events and dances are unknown and that's why these have huge potential to be promoted for the tourists who are always in the hunt of exploring new cultures.

Cultural Tourism has a special place in jaunsar Bawar because of its past civilization. Among the various motivating factors governing travel to Jaunsar Bawar, its cultural is undoubtedly the most important. For any foreigner a visit to Jaunsar Bawar must have a profound cultural impact and in its broader sense tourism in Jaunsar Bawar involves quite a large content of cultural contact.

Cultural tourism plays a major part in increasing national as well as international good will and understanding. There are many archaeological and historical monuments scattered throughout Jaunsar Bawar which provide opportunities to learn about ancient history and culture. According to a survey undertaken by the Pacific Area Travel Association, 54% of the tourists enjoy their stay

because of the beautiful creations of man-temples, heritage monuments and their art and architecture.

Music, dance and festivals, i.e Folk music (songs), folk dance and festivals i.e Folk music (songs), folk dance and festivals are also very important aspects of cultural tourism. The folk songs, dances and festivals become the primary attraction for large numbers of domestic as well as foreign tourists.

Those cultural attractions need to be exploited so that the domestic as well as foreign tourists could have an opportunity to witness the performance of professional dancers and musicians. Also the cultural events and sports associated with the festivals have an enormous scope for attracting tourists for cultural tourism.

Why Promotion of Jaunsar Culture

It is important to know the reasons for promoting the culture of Jaunsar Bawar:

One of the most overt results of promotion of a destination is that of encouraging cultural exchanges among different groups of people and introducing festivals, sports, its culture and environment to people from different parts of the world, both domestic and international. Elimination of misconception, development of good image can assure positive results for the respective destination which has yet to prove its identity as an ideal or sacred location for cultural tourism. In short, the geographical reasons are helpful in development of cultural tourism.

Apart from this, there are few important reasons that need to be mentioned. The major constraints associated with cultural tourism are as follows:

- a. Seasonality.
- b. Accommodation.
- c. Transportation.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To list the different cultural and food tourism options in Jaunsar Bawar.
2. To establish the benefits of cultural & food tourism to the economy of this area.
3. To analyze the factors enhancing the culture & food tourism in Jaunsar Bawar.

Type of Research: A descriptive research was used to study the potential of Cultural Tourism in Jaunsar Bawar Region.

Methods of Data Collection -Primary data was obtained from the local people by taking their personal interviews from a pre designed questionnaire.

Secondary Data – was collected by refereeing to the various videos available in public domain & literature, which talked in detail about the food & culture of Jaunsar Bawar.

Data Analysis & Interpretation

The interviews underscored the potential for Jaunsar Bawar to establish itself as a prominent destination for cultural and heritage tourism. Local heritage sites like Ashok's Rock Edict in Kalsi, the ancient village of Jagatgram, and the Lakhamandal temples were cited as significant attractions. Respondents believed that promoting the culture of Jaunsar Bawar within the national or international tourism industry could greatly enhance the sustainability of cultural and food tourism. They emphasized that many travellers, irrespective of their reasons for travel, are drawn to exploring local cultures and cuisines as a means to better understand the area and glean insights from its traditions. Additionally, 30 respondents highlighted the potential ripple effects of cultural and food tourism on various aspects of life in the region, including its economic landscape, employment opportunities, and entrepreneurial endeavours. This interconnectedness underscores the importance of adopting sustainable tourism practices that not only preserve cultural heritage but also contribute positively to the socio-economic development of Jaunsar Bawar.

Jaunsar Bawar's Cuisines

The food of Jaunsar Bawar has been heavily influenced over the centuries by the ingredients mostly grown locally. Cattle are regarded as a symbol of wealth across much of Jaunsar Bawar and they are use for dairy product as well as cuisines involving meat. Ground maize or corn is used as the basis for many meals. Maize flour is served with water/milk/buttermilk to form a stiff porridge and is considered as very high in protein and a very healthy food.

There are several dishes like Uluye, Pinnuye, Chillade, Khendadi , Koprodi , babar etc which forms a very healthy vegetarian dietary of people of Jaunsar Bawar during every major or minor festivals being celebrated there. These dishes are mostly consumed with locally made ghee or butter. Jaunsar Bawar is also famous for its pulses especially the Red Rajma of Chakrata that is making its name in the domestic market of India.

FIGURE 1. The Contribution of Local Food to Sustainable Development Within a Destination

Jaunsar is also a heaven for the non-vegetarian food lovers. There are several forms of non-vegetarian dishes of mutton, chicken & fish being cooked with the herbs & spices grown locally which adds a unique flavor to these foods. There is a festival month of Maagh in the month of January being celebrated all across Jaunsar when non-vegetarian food is extensively cooked and grand feast are organized by every families of the villages for local villagers as well as for the relatives coming over. People during this time also dry up the mutton so that it could be preserved for longer duration and this process also add up a unique flavor to the mutton dish.

In addition to a wide variety of food items, the locally made wines named as Pakhoi & Genghati are considered to be an elixir in this part, they are completely made of fruits, food-items & local herbs which adds specifically the amazing taste as well as the medicinal properties to the Gastronomy of Jaunsar Bawar. Their taste, health benefits and the meticulous planning in making them could actually play an important role in developing Eno-tourism in Jaunsar Bawar.

Discussions and Observations

The primary observation highlights that food and cultural tourism are yet to be fully established in the Jaunsar Bawar region, though they possess significant potential to serve as a pivotal focal point for the area. The comprehension of Jaunsar Bawar's rich heritage and culture remains relatively inadequate. Given its historical significance as a culturally representative region of the Himalayas, Jaunsar Bawar must earnestly strive to enhance the visibility and appreciation of its local culture and history among incoming tourists. Being renowned as the "Land of Mahasu," Jaunsar Bawar draws a substantial number of religious tourists from Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh, and Uttarakhand. In doing so, both directly and indirectly, Jaunsar Bawar creates numerous job opportunities and avenues for career growth in the tourism and service sectors, as well as fostering entrepreneurial expansion within the broader tourism industry.

Further observations reveal that all sectors of the service and corporate industries, spanning across various age groups, recognize the potential for heritage and cultural tourism to generate a plethora of employment opportunities. Through cultural and heritage tourism, additional revenue-generating prospects emerge for a diverse range of businesses, thereby facilitating business expansion and the creation of more job opportunities for locals. Consequently, as the region's tourism industry flourishes and expands, the local market and economy, along with numerous other enterprises, experience indirect growth.

As the allure of the region's culture and heritage continues to draw increasing numbers of visitors, infrastructure in the area undergoes enhancements, contributing to an overall improvement in the living standards of the local populace through advancements in education, healthcare, and other essential amenities. Consequently, this aids in mitigating the issue of migration, a prevalent concern in the Himalayan region.

Findings:

Interpretations derived from the analysis are as follows: The expansion of Cultural and Food tourism in the Jaunsar Bawar region is contingent upon increased information exposure and more extensive advertising, as indicated by the majority of respondents. Augmented amenities, such as quality homestays at various tourist locations, would elevate the status of tourism in Jaunsar Bawar. To heighten the exposure of Jaunsar Bawar's culture and history, more aggressive marketing strategies should be implemented for cultural and historic destinations. This heightened exposure would amplify awareness of Jaunsar's vibrant culture, attracting more visitors eager to experience it firsthand. Local communities and government entities should prioritize the dissemination of written materials concerning the region's culture and heritage to facilitate greater understanding among visitors. According to the primary findings, the sustainability of Heritage & Cultural tourism, coupled with the allure of local culture, would draw an increased number of tourists to the region, resulting in heightened profits and expanded job opportunities. The burgeoning culture and heritage tourism sector are also driving the growth of numerous ancillary and peripheral businesses within the tourism industry.

Recommendations & Suggestions:

1. Foster awareness about Cultural & Heritage tourism and encourage gastronomes to explore the region frequently.
2. Enhance the popularity of Jaunsar Bawar's culture through concerted efforts by local communities and authorities.
3. Disseminate literature on the region's history and culture at various tourist destinations to enrich the region's authenticity and significance.
4. Commemorate Jaunsar Bawar Day on June 24th on a grander scale, providing a platform for local artists to showcase the region's rich culture and for locals to exhibit the diverse culinary delights of Jaunsar Bawar.
5. The Uttarakhand tourist industry should undertake various promotional activities and organize cultural fairs and exhibitions to showcase the local heritage and culture, fostering favorable economic expansion.

6. Entrepreneurs in the Jaunsar Bawar region should adopt an aggressive approach to sell and promote their culture and heritage on various social media platforms and at events held in major cities such as Dehradun, Delhi, etc.
7. The Government of Uttarakhand should incentivize new businesses by offering lower lending rates and facilities, encouraging them to explore innovative ideas in cuisine and cultural tourism within Jaunsar Bawar. Schemes like the Home-stay initiative in Jaunsar Bawar should be promoted further, with technical support provided by specialists, enabling locals to effectively showcase the culture of Jaunsar Bawar.

Conclusion

Uttarakhand today is a lavish melody of various communities. Among these, the tribes of Uttarakhand hold an important place as they are the original natives of the land.

Major tribes of Uttarakhand are the Jaunsaris residing in the Jaunsar Bawar region. They are the largest tribe in terms of population and having a rich and unique culture in terms of temples, festivals, folk dances etc.

Jaunsar Bawar region is still not recognized and preferred as one of the important Cultural tourist destinations. The festivals of Jaunsar Bawar region like Magh Mela, Bissau etc folk dances and songs like Baradi Nati, Harul and temples such as Lakhamandal, Hanol etc are not famous among the domestic as well as international tourists and these are not even promoted by the Uttarakhand Tourism Department. The efforts taken up by Tourism departments and other Key players like GMVN are not enough to ensure tourist inflow in the region.

Cultural Tourism today is on the boom as more tourists are interested in understanding the culture of different areas and educating them. Hence by proper planning, implementation and by the mutual co-operation of Tourism Department and local public, Jaunsar Bawar can emerge as one of important Cultural tourist destinations in future and can have the following future advantages.

- (a) Good inflow of tourist arrival in Uttarakhand.**
- (b) Increase in state revenue by promoting cultural tourism in the Jaunsar Bawar region.**
- (c) Employment generation.**
- (d) Economic stability to local people.**

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